

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Xonturayeva Sayxuna

POTENTIAL CHALLENGES AND CONTROVERSIES ARISING FROM THE
USE OF BORROWED WORDS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND CULTURE

DRJI

Universal
Impact Factor

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